

COMPLEX COMPOUNDS OF BIGUANIDE WITH BI- AND TERVALENT METALS. PART VI. COPPER, NICKEL AND COBALT (*ic*) PHENYLBIGUANIDE-*p*-SULPHONIC ACID

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A new derivative of biguanide, phenylbiguanide-*p*-sulphonic acid, has been prepared from sulphamic acid and dicyandiamide. The substance behaves as an ampholyte and forms stable complexes with bivalent copper and nickel, as well as with trivalent cobalt. These complexes themselves behave as ampholytes and are insoluble in water. Co-ordination with copper and nickel is found to increase slightly the strength of the acid group of the ampholyte, while co-ordination with cobalt (*ic*) increases the strength of both the acidic and the basic groups.

In a series of papers Rây and co-workers (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1937, **14**, 671; 1938, **15**, 347, 350, 353; 1939, **16**, 617, 621, 629; 1941, **18**, 217, 239, 298, 609; 1942, **19**, 1) have described a large number of complex compounds of biguanide and its substitution products with bi- and trivalent metals like Cu, Ni, Pd, Cr and Co.

A new substituted biguanide, phenylbiguanide-*p*-sulphonic acid (I), has now been prepared and the present paper deals with the preparation, properties and the constitution of this derivative and its complex compounds with copper, nickel and cobalt.

Phenylbiguanide-*p*-sulphonic acid (I) exists evidently in the form of a *zwitter ion* (II), as both the acidic and basic groups in (I) are quite strong, while the corresponding conjugate basic and acidic groups in (II) are respectively neutral and weak.

[A_s = strong acid, B_s = strong base, A_w = weak acid, N = neutral].

The substance is, therefore, practically insoluble in water due to internal salt formation. Hence the complex compounds of this biguanide derivative with metallic elements were expected to be quite insoluble in water, resembling the inner metallic complexes and themselves behaving as ampholytes. These properties have been actually realised in the complexes described here. The study of such ampholytic complexes has got an additional interest of its own, as co-ordination with the metal atom might influence the strength of the acidic and basic groups of the molecule. It has been found that co-ordination with copper and nickel increases the acid character of the ampholyte, while that with cobaltic cobalt enhances somewhat the strengths of both the cationic acid and the anionic base, as demonstrated by the relative solubility of these complexes in alkalis and acids respectively.

where M^{aq} = $\frac{1}{2}$ Cu⁺⁺, $\frac{1}{2}$ Ni⁺⁺,
or, $\frac{1}{3}$ Co⁺⁺⁺.

In a line with the constitution of metal biguanide complexes in general, the structure of the phenylbiguanide-*p*-sulphonic acid complexes can be represented by (III).

These complexes are soluble in ammonia and alkalis without decomposition, but are insoluble in water or alcohol. The cobalt complex dissolves unchanged in dilute acids also.

The four co-ordinated metal complexes of copper and nickel are likely to exhibit *cis-trans* isomerism due to planar configuration (*cf.* Rây and Chakravarty, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 18, 609). But only one form, probably the *trans* (IV) of the copper and nickel phenylbiguanide, *p*-sulphonic acid, could be obtained in spite of all variations in their methods of preparation. The *cis* form seems to be unstable, due, evidently, to the close proximity which the two negative PhSO_3^- groups would assume in the molecule.

The octahedral cobaltic complex with (I) might also exist in three geometrically isomeric forms as indicated by V, VI and VII, of which the last (VII) with three PhSO_3^- groups away from one another should represent the most stable form.

The dot with bar indicates the position of PhSO_3^- groups.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Phenylbiguanide-*p*-sulphonic Acid.—Sulphanilic acid (2 g.), dicyandiamide (1.2 g.) and 30 c.c. of water were refluxed on a free flame for about 2 hours, when a silky, white solid separated out. This was filtered after cooling and washed with water. For purification it was dissolved in ammonia and reprecipitated by dilute HCl. {Found : N, 26.90; S (by peroxide fusion), 12.60. $\text{HO}_2\text{S}^-\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{C}_2\text{N}_2\text{H}_4$ requires N, 27.20; S, 12.45 per cent.}

The substance forms silky white crystals, very slightly acid to litmus. It is insoluble in cold water and organic solvents like alcohol, ether, acetone, etc., but soluble in strong acids as well as in dilute alkalis and ammonia, m.p. (decomp.), 265-68°.

Copper Phenylbiguanide-*p*-sulphonic Acid.—A solution of $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (1 g.) was added to a solution of phenylbiguanide-*p*-sulphonic acid (2.05 g.) in excess of ammonia at a temperature of 50-60°. Violet crystals separated on cooling. These were filtered, washed first with water, then with alcohol and finally dried in air. {Found : N, 23.66; Cu, 10.61, 10.64;

H_2O (loss at 90°), 3'0. $[Cu(BigPhSO_3H)_2]$, H_2O requires N, 23'59; Cu, 10'71; H_2O , 3'04 per cent). $HO_3S PhBigH$ = one molecule of phenylbiguanide-*p*-sulphonic acid.

The substance forms violet crystals, insoluble in water and alcohol, but dissolves readily in alkalis and ammonia. It is neutral to litmus and dissolves with decomposition in acetic acid and dilute mineral acids.

Nickel Phenylbiguanide-p-sulphonic Acid.—A solution of 2'2 g. of phenylbiguanide-*p*-sulphonic acid in ammonia was mixed with a solution of 1 g. of $NiCl_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ and the mixture was heated on the water-bath until yellow crystals appeared. These were washed and dried as before. {Found: N, 23'14; Ni, 9'59; H_2O (loss at 90°), 6'08. $[Ni(BigPhSO_3H)_2] \cdot 2H_2O$ requires N, 23'07; Ni, 9'67; H_2O , 5'93 per cent}.

The substance forms yellow crystals, insoluble in water or alcohol, but dissolves freely in alkalis and ammonia. It is not affected by very dilute mineral acids or 2*N* acetic acid, but dissolves in stronger acids with decomposition. It reacts neutral to litmus.

Cobaltic Phenylbiguanide-p-sulphonic Acid.—Phenylbiguanide-*p*-sulphonic acid (3'3 g.) in ammoniacal solution was added to an aqueous solution of 1 g. of $CoCl_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ and a vigorous current of air was passed through the mixture till it was practically free from ammonia. The insoluble product was dissolved with addition of fresh ammonia and the solution filtered. The filtrate was evaporated on the water-bath to remove the major quantity of ammonia. The mixture was cooled and allowed to stand overnight in the cold. The red crystals that separated were washed and dried as usual. {Found: N, 22'76; Co, 6'33; H_2O (loss at 90°), 9'96. $[Co(BigPhSO_3H)_3] \cdot 5H_2O$ requires N, 22'90; Co, 6'42; H_2O , 9'82 per cent}.

The substance forms red crystals, neutral to litmus. It is only slightly soluble in cold water, but more in hot water. The substance behaves as an ampholyte and dissolves readily in acids, alkalis and ammonia without decomposition.